

HFNMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION
RGN20. COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION.
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

- a. Outline three (3) roles each of the following rehabilitation team members
- i. Physiotherapist
 - ii. Social worker
 - iii. Psychologist
- 9 marks
- b. State the **three (3)** principles of counseling
- 3marks
- c. List the **two (2)** goals of counseling
- 2marks
- d. Enumerate **eight (8)** duties of a counsellor to the disable
- 4marks
- e. Enumerate **two (2)** functions of communication boards to the child
- 2marks

QUESTION TWO

Tawiah, a 20 year old disable person with mobility impairment is living in your community and will need some form of rehabilitation.

- a. Mention and explain five roles of the nurse in the rehabilitation of Tawiah? - 10 marks
- b. Give **four (4)** benefits of rehabilitation to Tawiah. - 4 marks
- c. State the three (3) types of rehabilitation - 3marks
- d. Mention three (3) tools that will be used in rehabilitating Tawiah - 3marks

QUESTION THREE

The incidence of disability has always been on the increasing trend and about 60% of disabilities could have been prevented.

- a. As a nurse, how will you prevent disabilities under the following in the community?
- i. Primordial
 - ii. Primary
 - iii. Secondary
 - iv. Tertiary
- 8 marks
- b. Mr. Kontor, a 50 year old man with visual impairment is living in your community and will need some empowerment to cope with his disabilities. State and explain **five (5)** ways by which you can empower him.
- 10 marks
- c. State **four(4)** rehabilitation tools that you will recommend for Mr. Kontor
- 2marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- AUGUST, 2021

RGN21. COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark*

QUESTION ONE

Community based rehabilitation (CBR) is an organized program starting with segregation of the disabled from able.

- a. Outline the five(5) basic principles of the community based rehabilitation programme - 5 marks
- b. Describe the five(5) basic principles you have outlined in (a) above - 10 marks
- c. State the Ten(10) stake holders in the community based rehabilitation programme - 5 marks

QUESTION TWO

Tawiah, a 20 year old disable person with mobility impairment is living in your community and will need some form of rehabilitation; you have been tasked to implement the community based rehabilitation (CBR) programme since it is the only way to bring rehabilitation know-how to villages and urban slums.

- a. Mention the **eight(8)** steps you follow to implement the programme - 8 marks
- b. State **three(3)** challenges you are likely to face in your implementation process - 3 marks
- c. Enumerate **six(6)** essential components of a CBR programme - 6 marks
- d. In 2000, the UN Member States adopted the Millennium Declaration and set eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to guide the implementation of the Declaration. All the goals are relevant to disability and three goals are of particular concern to PWDs and their families: Mention **these three(3)** goals - 3 marks

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Tettey, a 60 year old man with visual impairment is living in your community and will need some empowerment to cope with his disabilities.

- a. State and explain **four (4)** ways by which you can empower him. - 8marks
- b. State **four(4)** rehabilitation tools that you will recommend for Mr. Tettey - 2marks

Rehabilitation provides a long continuum of care ranging from hospital care to rehabilitation in the community.

- c. Describe **five (5)** roles of a nurse in the rehabilitation process of the disable. - 10 Marks

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HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RGN 19 : COMMUNITY REHABILITATION (RGN 321)
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Counselling is one of the approaches most frequently used in health education to help individuals and families with disabilities.

- a. State the **four (4)** principles of counseling - 4 marks
- b. List the **two (2)** goals of counseling - 2 marks
- c. Enumerate **ten (10)** duties of a counsellor to the disabled - 10 marks
- d. Community based rehabilitation was initiated by WHO as part of PHC and it has four models. Mention these **four (4)** models of community-based rehabilitation - 4 marks

QUESTION TWO

Rehabilitation is the restoration of an individual or a part to normal or near normal function after a disabling disease.

- a. Explain the following role of the nurse in rehabilitation - 10 Marks
 - i. Patient/family advocate
 - ii. Coordinator of care
 - iii. Care provider
 - iv. Health education/patient education
 - v. Support and counselling
- b. Give **four (4)** benefits of rehabilitation - 4 marks
- c. State the three **(3)** types of rehabilitation - 3 marks
- d. Mention six **(6)** tools used in rehabilitation - 3 marks

QUESTION THREE

The causes of disability vary especially as a person ages and is numerous.

- a. Enumerate **three (3)** causes of each of the following disabilities - 9 marks
 - i. Speech difficulties
 - ii. Mobility difficulties
 - iii. Intellectual challenge
 - b. State and explain **five (5)** ways of empowering people with disability - 10 marks
- While the rehabilitation gap cannot be closed in any quick or easy way Community Based Rehabilitation is considered one of the most practical and efficient rehabilitation approaches.
- c. State **two (2)** stakeholders in community based rehabilitation - 1 mark

QUESTION FOUR

Akua is 12 months old, but is not able to walk as compared to her peers; paediatric examination reveals that Akua is suffering from developmental delay.

- a. State and explain the **four (4)** warning signs of developmental delay - 12 marks
- b. State the **two (2)** ways by which you can identify developmental delay in children - 2 marks
- c. List **six (6)** intervention services available for Akua - 6marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
DIPLOMA 14.HRGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Define the following terms as used in CBR
- i. Rehabilitation - 2 marks
 - ii. Community Based Rehabilitation - 2 marks
- b. State two (2) objectives of CBR - 2 marks
- c. As a member of the rehabilitation team what role would you play in disability prevention - 14 marks

Question Two

The principles of a Community Based Rehabilitation programme are said to be overlapping, complimentary and interdependent and that they cannot be separated one from the other

- a. List the five (5) principles - 5 marks
- b. Explain each of the five principles listed above - 10 marks
- c. Identify five challenges of Community Based Rehabilitation - 5 marks

Question Three

An N.G.O visited a school of the blind with the aim of empowering the blind students to gain some level of Independence

- a. Define the term empowerment - 1 mark
- b. Explain five (5) schemes that can be adopted by the NGO to empower the students - 10 marks
- c. i. State one difference between institutional rehabilitation and out-reach rehabilitation - 2 marks
- ii. Give one limitation each of institutional based rehabilitation and out- reach rehabilitation - 2marks
- d. State one role of the following rehabilitation team members
- i. Physiotherapist
 - ii. Occupational therapist
 - iii. Psychiatrist
 - iv. Social worker
 - v. Speech and language pathologist

Question Four

5 marks

Kankam, a 10 year old blind boy was brought to the OPD of Saint Mary Theresa Hospital by the mother with the history of fever, headache and chills. Upon physical examination, the physician detected that Kankam had herniplegia with several other impairments and disabilities. After treatment, he referred Kankam to a rehabilitation centre.

- a. Define the following
- i. impairment - 1 marks
 - ii. Disability - 1 mark
 - iii. Handicap - 1 mark
- b. Explain five (5) causes of disability - 10 marks
- c. Explain the three (3) main forms of disability - 6 marks
- d. State the goal of Primary Prevention of disability - 1 mark

NMTC-BEREKUM
DIPLOMA 13 HRGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. State the three (3) main factors leading to impairment, disability and handicap - 3 marks
- b. Explain four (4) effects each of disability on the individual, the family and the nation at large - 12marks
- Rehabilitation seeks to change the socio – economic situation of peoples with disabilities
- i. List two (2) theories that can be used to illustrate these changes - 2 marks
- ii. Explain one of the theories stated above - 3 marks

Question Two

- a. Explain the following terms in the context of health;
- i. Impairment - 2 marks
- ii. Disability - 2 marks
- iii. Handicap - 2 marks
- b. Describe three (3) main types of rehabilitation - 12marks
- c. State the four (4) models of community based rehabilitation - 2 marks

Question Three

- Offi Mensah, 42 years old former had an amputation of the right arm.
- a. As a member of the CBR team how would you help to empower Mr. Mensah - 12 marks
- b. State five (5) types of disability in CBR - 5 marks
- c. Defined community based Rehabilitation - 3 marks

Question Four

- a. Define the term Rehabilitation - 2 marks
- b. State three (3) objectives of Rehabilitation - 3marks
- c. As a member of the rehabilitation team what role would you play in disability prevention?
Discuss - 15marks

HOLY FAMILY NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION MAY 2016
RGN 16 RGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 hours

Instruction:

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark*

Question One

- a. Explain the following terms in the context of health
- i. Handicap - 2 marks
 - ii. Community Based Rehabilitation - 2 marks
- b. Outline four attitudes that everyone can adopt in order to empower people with disability - 4 marks
- c. What role would you play in the Rehabilitation process and disability prevention - 12 marks

Question Two

Mr. Mumuni, a 45 year old man was run over by a tipper truck during the course of running his business as a mobile phone credit vendor. He was rushed to the Holy Family Hospital and eventually had amputation of both legs in order to save his life. He has a wife and four children.

- a. Explain any three(3) Social Factors that can cause a disability of this kind - 4 marks
- b. Discuss seven (7) effects of the disability on Mr. Mumuni and his family - 7 marks
- c. As a member of the Rehabilitation Team what measures would you put in place to help empower Mr. Mumuni
- i. Psychologically - 3 marks
 - ii. Physically - 3 marks
 - iii. Socially - 3 marks

Question Three

The disabled and their families are central to every rehabilitation program, because rehabilitation seeks to change the socio-economic situation of these people. It is therefore important that they themselves tell what they need in order to help meet them.

- a. State the five (5) expressed Rehabilitation needs of people with disabilities - 5marks
- b. What is the role of the DPO in the CBR program - 3 marks
- c. Outline six (6) challenges of the CBR program - 6 marks
- d. Explain three (3) basic principles of a CBR - 6 marks

Question Four

- a. Explain the types of Rehabilitation Teams that may work together - 6marks
- b. State and explain the five(5) main areas of child development - 10 marks
- c. List eight (8) causes of developmental delay - 4 marks

INDEX NUMBER
HFNMTC- BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2017
RGN 17: COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Mr. Wilder was involved in a motor accident and subsequently developed mobility difficulties and now depends on under arm crutches to be able to move around.

- a. Define Disability according to the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) - 2 marks
- b. Explain the following forms of disability - 2 marks
- i. Physical disability - 3 marks
 - ii. Psychological disability - 3 marks
 - iii. Social disability - 3 marks
- c. Outline SIX causes of mobility difficulties - 3 marks
- d. Explain the following levels of disability prevention: - 3 marks
- i. Primary prevention - 2 marks
 - ii. Secondary prevention - 2 marks
 - iii. Tertiary prevention - 2 marks

Question Two

Mrs. Mawuli, 27 years old is physically challenged and now undergoing rehabilitation.

- a. Explain the term Rehabilitation to a first year student nurse - 2 marks
- b. What is community Based Rehabilitation - 4 marks
- c. Enumerate Seven(7) roles of the nurse in Rehabilitation - 7 marks
- d. Explain the following types of Rehabilitation
- i. Institution based rehabilitation - 2 marks
 - ii. Outreach based rehabilitation - 2 marks
- e. Mention SIX tools and gadgets used for rehabilitation - 3 marks

Question Three

- a. Mr. Kwasi Mensah 50 years old diabetic is admitted to your ward after an above knee amputation
- i. In what five (5) ways are you going to empower Mr. Mensah - 10 marks
- b. Outline three importance of communication boards used in Rehabilitation - 3 marks
- c. State four benefits of rehabilitation - 4 marks
- d. Mention six (6) causes of intellectual challenge - 3 marks

Question Four

Outline four roles each of the following rehabilitation team members

- a. Physiotherapist - 4 marks
- b. Occupational therapist - 4 marks
- c. Social worker - 4 marks
- d. Vocational counsellor - 4 marks
- e. Psychologist - 4 marks

HFNMTC- BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2018
D 18: COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

Mr. Nyamekye, 40 years old is physically challenged and now undergoing rehabilitation.

- | | | |
|--|---|---------|
| a. Explain the term Rehabilitation to a first year student nurse | - | 2 marks |
| b. Mention the three levels of rehabilitation | - | 3 marks |
| c. Enumerate EIGHT (8) roles of the nurse in Rehabilitation | - | 8 marks |
| d. Explain the following types of Rehabilitation | | |
| i. Institution based rehabilitation | - | 2 marks |
| ii. Outreach based rehabilitation | - | 2 marks |
| e. Mention SIX (6) tools and gadgets used for rehabilitation | - | 3 marks |

Question Two

- | | | |
|--|---|----------|
| a. State and explain five (5) ways of empowering people with disability | - | 10 marks |
| b. Outline three importance of communication boards used in Rehabilitation | - | 3 marks |
| c. State four (4) benefits of rehabilitation | - | 4 marks |
| d. Mention six (6) causes of intellectual challenge | - | 3 marks |

Question Three

Outline four (4) roles each of the following rehabilitation team members

- | | | |
|---------------------------|---|---------|
| a. Physiotherapist | - | 4 marks |
| b. Occupational therapist | - | 4 marks |
| c. Social worker | - | 4 marks |
| d. Vocational counsellor | - | 4 marks |
| e. Psychologist | - | 4 marks |

Question Four

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| a. Explain the following forms of disabilities; | | |
| i. Physical Disability | - | 3 marks |
| ii. Psychological disability | - | 3 marks |
| bi. What is community Based Rehabilitation | - | 2marks |
| ii. State the four (4) models of community based rehabilitation | - | 4marks |
| c. Outline four (4) duties each of the following | | |
| i. Psychiatrist | - | 4 marks |
| ii. Speech therapist | - | 4 marks |

NMTC-BEREKUM
DIPLOMA 13 HRGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

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- Each question carries 20 marks.
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Question One

- a. State the three (3) main factors leading to impairment, disability and handicap - 3 marks
- Explain four (4) effects each of disability on the individual, the family and the nation at large - 12marks
- c. Rehabilitation seeks to change the socio – economic situation of peoples with disabilities
- i. List two (2) theories that can be used to illustrate these changes - 2 marks
- ii. Explain one of the theories stated above - 3 marks

Question Two

- a. Explain the following terms in the context of health;
- i. Impairment - 2 marks
- ii. Disability - 2 marks
- iii. Handicap - 2 marks
- b. Describe three (3) main types of rehabilitation - 12marks
- State the four (4) models of community based rehabilitation - 2 marks

Question Three

Mr. Kofi Mensah, 42 years old former had an amputation of the right arm.

- a. As a member of the CBR team how would you help to empower Mr. Mensah - 12 marks
- b. State five (5) types of disability in CBR - 5 marks
- c. Defined community based Rehabilitation - 3 marks

Question Four

- a. Define the term Rehabilitation - 2 marks
- b. State three (3) objectives of Rehabilitation - 3marks
- c. As a member of the rehabilitation team what role would you play in disability prevention?
Discuss - 15marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
DIPLOMA 14.HRGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
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- a. Define the following terms as used in CBR
- i. Rehabilitation - 2 marks
 - ii. Community Based Rehabilitation - 2 marks
- b. State two (2) objectives of CBR - 2 marks
- c. As a member of the rehabilitation team what role would you play in disability prevention - 14 marks

Question Two

The principles of a Community Based Rehabilitation programme are said to be overlapping, complimentary and interdependent and that they cannot be separated one from the other

- a. List the five (5) principles - 5 marks
- b. Explain each of the five principles listed above - 10 marks
- c. Identify five challenges of Community Based Rehabilitation - 5 marks

Question Three

An N.G.O visited a school of the blind with the aim of empowering the blind students to gain some level of independence

- a. Define the term empowerment - 1 mark
- b. Explain five (5) schemes that can be adopted by the NGO to empower the students - 10 marks
- c. i. State one difference between institutional rehabilitation and out-reach rehabilitation - 2 marks
- ii. Give one limitation each of institutional based rehabilitation and out- reach rehabilitation - 2marks
- d. State one role of the following rehabilitation team members
- i. Physiotherapist
 - ii. Occupational therapist
 - iii. Psychiatrist
 - iv. Social worker
 - v. Speech and language pathologist
- 5 marks

Question Four

Kankam, a 10 year old blind boy was brought to the OPD of Saint Mary Theresa Hospital by the mother with the history of fever, headache and chills. Upon physical examination, the physician detected that Kankam had herniplegia with several other impairments and disabilities. After treatment, he referred Kankam to a rehabilitation centre.

- a. Define the following
- i. impairment - 1 marks
 - ii. Disability - 1 mark
 - iii. Handicap - 1 mark
- b. Explain five (5) causes of disability - 10 marks
- c. Explain the three (3) main forms of disability - 6 marks
- d. State the goal of Primary Prevention of disability - 1 mark

HOLY FAMILY NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION MAY 2016
RGN 16 RGN 062 COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 hours

Instruction:

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Question Two

Mr. Mumuni, a 45 year old man was run over by a tipper truck during the course of running his business as a mobile phone credit vendor. He was rushed to the Holy Family Hospital and eventually had amputation of both legs in order to save his life. He has a wife and four children.

- a. Explain any three(3) Social Factors that can cause a disability of this kind - 4 marks
- b. Discuss seven (7) effects of the disability on Mr. Mumuni and his family - 7 marks
- c. As a member of the Rehabilitation Team what measures would you put in place to help empower Mr. Mumuni
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 - ii. Physically - 3 marks
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The disabled and their families are central to every rehabilitation program, because rehabilitation seeks to change the socio-economic situation of these people. It is therefore important that they themselves tell what they need in order to help meet them.

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- b. What is the role of the DPO in the CBR program - 3 marks
- c. Outline six (6) challenges of the CBR program - 6 marks
- d. Explain three (3) basic principles of a CBR - 6 marks

Question Four

- a. Explain the types of Rehabilitation Teams that may work together - 6marks
- b. State and explain the five(5) main areas of child development - 10 marks
- c. List eight (8) causes of developmental delay - 4 marks